

A BRIEF NOTE ON THE FINDING OF SPECIMENS OF CRABHOLE MOSQUITOES (*Deinocerites magnus* Theobald, 1901) (DIPTERA: CULICIDAE) IN CHUAO COMMUNITY, IN THE COAST OF ARAGUA STATE (BOLIVARIAN REPUBLIC OF VENEZUELA)

UNA NOTA SUCINTA SOBRE EL HALLAZGO DE EJEMPLARES DE MOSQUITOS DE CUEVAS DE CANGREJO (*Deinocerites magnus* Theobald, 1901) (DIPTERA: CULICIDAE) EN EL LITORAL DE LA COMUNIDAD DE CHUAO DEL ESTADO ARAGUA (REPÚBLICA BOLIVARIANA DE VENEZUELA)

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ABSTRACT

In this brief note we wish to report the finding of the Crabhole Mosquito (*Deinocerites magnus* Theobald, 1901), in order to report its presence on a Venezuelan beach (Chuaos beach, Aragua state, Venezuela), since it is a species incriminated in the transmission of Venezuelan Equine Encephalitis.

KEY WORDS: Culicidae, crabs, Venezuelan Equine Encephalitis.

RESUMEN

En esta sucinta nota deseamos reportar el hallazgo del mosquito de cueva de cangrejos (*Deinocerites magnus* Theobald, 1901), con el objeto de informar su presencia en una playa venezolana (playa de Chuao, estado Aragua, Venezuela), ya que se trata de una especie incriminada en la transmisión de la Encefalitis Equina Venezolana.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Culicidae, cangrejos, Encefalitis Equina Venezolana.

Dear Editor

In previous epidemiological studies of visceral Leishmaniasis, carried out by us on the coast of the Aragua state, in the town of Chuao (Bolivarian Republic of Venezuela), we were able to collect around 1500 specimens of mosquitoes of various genera and species (*Lutzomia*, *Aedes*, *Culex* and *Deinocerites*) using the Shannon trap, light lamps, and Castro's aspirators, which were classified by the entomologist Ignacio Ortiz† (Pifano *et al.* 1976) and Domingo Morales†. These collections were kept in our laboratory and actually reviewing these reports, we have found identified specimens of *Deinocerites magnus*, which had not been previously described in Chuao (Aragua, state, Venezuela) by other authors. We have opted to report this simple finding in a beach with touristic presence, since this mosquito is described as a vector of Venezuelan equine encephalitis (VEE), an endemic/epidemic disease of western Venezuela. In our captures, at Chuao area, we also were able to also find specimens of *Deinocerites atlanticus* (Pifano *et al.* 1976) that

certainly had been previously reported in this region (Adames 1971, Dickerman *et al.* 1986), in which we also had observed in other collections carried out by us in the Venezuelan Goajira (Rodríguez-Acosta & Morales 1974), on the occasion of a study of different Venezuelan geographic leishmaniasis vectors (Phlebotominae) from the Venezuelan Coast (Rodríguez *et al.* 1976).

Mosquitoes (*Deinocerites magnus*) adults described in this study were collected using manual aspirators (Castro's aspirators) (Fig. 1) during dry season (March) at the beach area from Chuao town, Aragua state, Venezuela) (Fig. 1) at Latitude: 10°29'31"N - Longitude: 67°31'40"W (Fig. 1). A sample of 90 specimens fitting to Culicidae family were gathered, searching crabholes to which the adults appear to be confined as in the case of *Deinocerites* (Adames 1971) of which 15 were chosen for this study, as they were in suitable condition and agreeing to the morphological characteristics belonged to the species *Deinocerites magnus*, using illustrative keys (Adames 1971,

Forattini 2002, van der Beek *et al.* 2020).

hollows and the manual aspirator in the current work is shown in Figure 1.

The studied geographical distribution, crab

Figure 1. Geographical distribution area. Crab spp. hollows, female *D. magnus* image and mosquitoes' aspirator device.

***Deinocerites magnus* (Theobald, 1901)**

Adults of *D. magnus* were captured in crab holes at several areas on Chuao beach municipality (Fig. 1).

Head widest at about the level of base of antennae; abdominal segment 10 with two separated sclerotized plates*D. magnus* (van der Beek *et al.* 2020).

Characteristic keys

Female

The average values of the reported analysis of the specimens showed: *A)* Head: narrow scales with apex very light brown; raised cream-colored scales; extensive scales on whitish lateral spot. *B)* Proboscis with an average of 1.96 mm. *C)* Abdomen of approximately 2.30 mm. *D)* Dark mesonotum; Generally clear pleural integument, very contrasting with the much darker mesonotal integument. *E)* Antenna: Torus occasionally with 1 scale; exceeding proboscis from apex of flagella segment 8. *F)* Wing: an average size of 2.36 mm. *G)* Anterior femur 1.50 mm. *H)* Simple metameron; meron, metameron and whitish metapleuron. *I)* Legs: very clear coxal integument, almost white.....*D. magnus*.

Comments

Most of the mosquitoes' species were found during the dry season. However, *D. magnus* was always present, regardless of weather conditions. We did not obtain published records of a specific identification of a crab species, with which it can be associated with *D. magnus*. However, since bionomics point of view, all species of the *Deinocerites* genus normally use as breeding sites, as well as adult latent sites, hollows of land crabs of the families Gecarcinidae and Ocypodidae (Adames 1971). In these habitual *Deinocerites* breeding sites *D. magnus* have been reported in some Caribbean islands, such as Saint Martin (van der Kuyp 1948: reported as cancer; van der Beek *et al.* 2020) and in crabholes from Trinidad and Granada (Adames 1971). National authors have reported this species for Anzoátegui, Miranda, Sucre, Delta Amacuro states and Capital District (Venezuela) (Cova-Garcia *et al.* 1971, Liria & Navarro 1999).

Antenna considerable longer than proboscis; flagella segment 1 double as long as clypeus and clearly longer than segment 2.....*D. magnus* (Adames 1971).

The adults of *Deinocerites* appear selected

nocturnal or crepuscular activity, resting during the day in the superior parts of crabholes (Dyar 1928). When disrupted the adults do not fly far and quickly come back to the crabholes (Adames 1971).

The main objective of this note is to interest general entomologists, which can make an exhaustive study of the presence of *D. magnus* on the Venezuelan central coast in a high touristic place; as the *Deinocerites* genus could consider as important in Collective Health, since some *Deinocerites* species are sporadically infected with arboviruses, including Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus (VEE) and St. Louis encephalitis virus (SLEV) (Galindo *et al.* 1966).

Among the Group IV of Togaviridae viruses, Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus (VEE) is described as a New World alphavirus. These New World alphavirus, including Eastern equine encephalitis virus (VEEV) have established independently from those of the Old World, such as Chikungunya virus (CHIKV) (Garmashova *et al.* 2006). VEE and VEEV infects birds, equines, humans, snakes and other vertebrates by arbovectors mosquitoes. It has been described that VEE and VEEV are particularly grievous for horses and mules, with a median fatality ratio, in these equines, of 20-80% (Deardorff *et al.* 2009).

In humans, primary VEE and VEEV infections are habitually overcome by natural immune responses; nonetheless, nearby 14% of the human's patients present neurological symptoms and around 1% of the infections result in lethal acute encephalitis (Johnson & Martin 1974).

It should be epidemiologically important to know that this arbovectors have been described in the Chuao's geographical area.

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